

22NRM03 MetHyTrucks

Deliverable 6 - Good practice guide on the validation of sampling systems at HD-HRS

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Glossary

NMHC: non-methane hydrocarbons

TS: total sulphur

THC: total hydrocarbons

LD: Light-Duty

HD: Heavy-Duty

HRS: Hydrogen Refuelling station

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1 Summary

This document describes a validation protocol for sampling systems used to collect samples of hydrogen at an HRS for subsequent purity analysis following for example EN 17124:2022 or ISO 14687:2025 standards. It is mostly based on knowledge gathered from experiments performed during the MetroHyVe2 and MetHyTrucks projects. However, full validation of hydrogen sampling systems remains challenging due to the complexity of replicating real refuelling conditions and the difficulty of assessing trace contaminants with high confidence. A combined strategy—integrating field validation, laboratory testing, and equivalence assessment—therefore represents the most robust and pragmatic approach.

2 Introduction

This document outlines a validation protocol for sampling systems used to collect samples of hydrogen at hydrogen refuelling stations (HRSs) for subsequent purity analysis following, for example EN 17124:2022 [1] or ISO 14687:2025 [2] standards. The use of a sampling system capable of delivering representative hydrogen samples is essential for reliable hydrogen quality assessment. This, in turn, supports confidence among heavy-duty (HD) vehicle owners, HRS operators, and other stakeholders, thereby facilitating the broader adoption of hydrogen as a fuel for HD applications.

For the sampling systems, two validation methods are discussed: field or laboratory validation (or at a validation facility). Each of these methods has limitations which are also discussed in the next section of this document. In addition, an example of field validation is presented to illustrate how a validation exercise may be conducted in practice.

In contrast to the validation of analytical methods—where performance characteristics can typically be established using measurements of real samples and reference materials—the validation of sampling systems is inherently more complex. This document constitutes the final version of the protocol and is based on the draft version (A3.2.2), the outcomes of the related teleconferences (A3.2.3), and additional activities conducted within the project. Requirements for online monitoring are outside the scope of this report.

3 Limitations

3.1 – Field validation

An important limitation of field validation is that the hydrogen quality at the nozzle is often of high purity and thus no (or few) contaminants are detected [3] [4]. Due to the absence of contaminants in the hydrogen, any validation process will therefore only give information about the few compound(s) present above the limit of detection of the analytical methods.

In ISO 19880-8:2019 [5], the probability of occurrence (likelihood that impurities can be above the threshold value) for each impurity or family of impurities is given in different tables (for instance B.4 and B.5) and has been summarized in the Table 1):

Table 1 – Probability of occurrence of impurities according to ISO19880-8. The different classes are given by: 0: practically impossible, 1: very rare; 10^{-6} , 2: rare: 10^{-5} , 3: possible: 10^{-4} , 4: frequent, often

	Off-site SMR	Pipeline distribution	Refuelling station	Alkaline electrolysis
N ₂	3	1	3	3
Ar	2	0	0	1

O ₂	0	1	2	2
CO ₂	0	0	0	0
CO	4	0	0	0
CH ₄	2	0	0	0
H ₂ O	0	0	1	2
TS	0	0	1	0
NH ₃	0	0	0	0
THC	0	0	2	0
HCHO	1	0	0	0
HCOOH	0	0	0	0
Halogens	0	0	0	0
Helium	0	0	0	0

TS: total sulphur; THC: total hydrocarbons

Based on this, it is highly probable that field validation will not provide any information regarding the ability of the sampling systems to collect a sample of hydrogen that is representative of the hydrogen dispensed at the station with regards to ammonia, formic acid, halogens, carbon dioxide and helium. Little or no information should be obtained for total sulfur and formaldehyde [4] [3] [6] [7].

However, based on the outcomes of the HyQuality Europe project, the occurrence of many contaminants appears to be much higher [8] than assumed earlier on (e.g., ISO 19880-8:2019). In particular this holds for H₂O: in a whopping 25% (55 out of 219 results, database assessed on 20 May 2026) of the samples, the EN17124 threshold value was exceeded. In second place is O₂, with 7% exceedances (15 out of 225). Based on this, a field validation is much more likely to provide useful information for H₂O and in a lesser extend for O₂ than based on earlier contamination data. A field validation is expected to be of less use for other impurities (only validating the absence of contamination).

3.2 – Laboratory or facility validation

Another approach is to simulate a sampling event (or an event close to a refuelling event) using reference gas cylinders with known amount fractions of contaminants. This allows to study more contaminants including, for instance, reactive species that are rarely found in real hydrogen samples. Ideally tests should be conducted with contaminants both above and below the threshold values. A limitation of such realisation is mainly due to technical issues, including the difficulties in simulating refuelling conditions (T, P, flow).

3.3 – Advantages and disadvantages of field or laboratory validation

Table 2 summarizes the advantages and disadvantages of the two methods for validation

Table 2 – Advantages and disadvantages of the field and laboratory validation

	Field validation	Laboratory validation
Pro	Most realistic validation using conditions (e.g. flow rates and pressure) that are hard to achieve via other means.	Relatively simple to prepare samples around or above the ISO threshold.

Most of the impurities except for H₂O will be well below the ISO threshold and some even below the LOQ of the operated analysers.

Difficult to simulate the refuelling conditions (T, P and flow)

Con

Impact: Validation only valid for few impurities, results for the other impurities can only be estimated based on e.g., similarity of chemical and physical properties.

Impact: Validation not done under realistic conditions. This may impact the validity of the results, for H₂O but it could also affect other impurities.

4 Influence of variability parameters on the validation

Good knowledge of the variability parameters (e.g., impact of pressure, temperature, and flow) is a prerequisite for all validation exercises. Different studies have shown that proper validation of sampling systems requires appropriate control over the HRS parameters.

Experiments realised during MetroHyVe2 project [9] where hydrogen samples were collected from different storage banks and analysed with regards to nitrogen, water, carbon dioxide and oxygen showed that the quality of hydrogen varied in the different storage banks. This variation mostly occurred for carbon dioxide (up to a factor 7, from 0.2 ppm up to approximately 1.4 ppm), water (up to a factor 4, from 20 ppm up to about 80 ppm) and nitrogen (up to a factor of 2-2.5 from approximately 130 to 315 ppm). The heat exchanger used for pre-cooling of the fuel may influence the water amount fraction in the hydrogen gas as some water may accumulate inside and be released more or less randomly.

During a sampling exercise performed as part of MetroHyVe2 to compare different sampling systems, the origin of the sampled gas was studied. It was observed that even if the samplings with the different sampling systems were performed consecutively, the hydrogen didn't originate from the same storage bank. Moreover, the hydrogen sampled with a parallel sampling system may originate from different storage banks while the gas sampled with the serial sampling system originated only from one bank.

The origin of the hydrogen is related to the refuelling protocols for parallel sampling and the quantity of hydrogen in the storage banks. The mechanism of bank switching is not defined in refuelling protocols (e.g. SAE J2601) but implemented in HRS control (e.g., in dependence on pressure difference).

The experiments realised during MetroHyVe 2 tend to demonstrate that the precooling steps may have an impact on the composition of the hydrogen (at least for water) while no influence of the filling rate could be seen.

Experiments conducted during the MetHyTrucks project confirmed the importance of having a thorough understanding of the parameters at the hydrogen refuelling station (HRS). Based on the outcomes of these experimental campaigns, the following recommendations were proposed:

- For direct sampling devices: perform sampling under representative operating conditions—matching delivery temperature and nominal pressure (70 MPa for H70 nozzle and 35 MPa for H35 nozzle if possible but at least 20 MPa), verifying storage homogeneity, and ensure adequate nozzle purging, purge a minimum of 70 g.
- For parallel sampling devices: conduct sampling under representative refuelling conditions. This includes, in coordination with the station operator, ensuring the homogeneity of the storage banks and, where possible, recording which storage bank is used for each refuelling event, as well as documenting the fuelling protocol applied and confirming that refuelling proceeds under normal operating conditions (e.g. avoiding aborted or unusually slow refuelling events).

5 Validation purposes and principles

The validation exercise shall demonstrate that the system is fit-for-purpose. One of the best ways to demonstrate this is by determining the recovery yield. The recovery yield is estimated by comparing the known amount fraction of impurities in hydrogen dispensed at an HRS to the values obtained from the analysis of the hydrogen sampled by the sampling system. However, in many cases, the amount fraction of the impurities in the dispensed hydrogen is not accurately known. There are two ways to go around this issue:

- 1) Validate the system at a facility with known amount fractions of impurities (see section 9)
- 2) Compare the composition of the hydrogen collected by the system to the hydrogen quality in the storage bank.

The second option needs careful considerations. Experiments performed during MetHyTrucks project demonstrated a significant bias between the water amount fraction present in the HRS storage system and the actual amount fraction delivered to an FCEV. Therefore, the water amount fraction measured directly from the HRS storage is not considered representative and may provide an inaccurate basis for evaluating the water amount fraction supplied at the nozzle.

While full validation of sampling systems may remain challenging, demonstrating equivalence between two systems can still provide valuable insights. However, equivalence does not imply trueness, but rather mutual consistency under the tested conditions.

In an equivalence assessment exercise, two systems are considered equivalent if the results of the purity analysis obtained for both systems agree. To avoid the risks that the two systems both result in non-representative hydrogen compositions, one of the systems is preferably a reference system (for which some kind of validation has already been performed).

To avoid drawing false conclusions, it is important to ensure that the systems that will be compared sample the same quality/source of hydrogen, so it is preferable that the systems are tested using the same storage bank. Another precaution is to control the variable parameters as much as technically possible. As these validation exercises are time-consuming and very expensive (they require a lot of preparation time, including risk assessment), compromises are needed; for example, validation will be done at only one set of parameters (flow, pressure, temperature) and it is assumed that the results of the validation exercises are also applicable to other conditions.

The time interval during the test of the two systems needs to be reduced to a minimum and the parameters of the station need to be controlled. Even in that case, there is no guarantee that the quality of the hydrogen will remain the same during the sampling time (the hydrogen sampled with a parallel sampling system may originate from different storage banks while the gas sampled with the serial sampling system originated only from one bank). To avoid measurement errors due to changes in hydrogen concentration during consecutive samplings with different sampling systems, one approach would be to connect "gas parallel" systems in series while refuelling a pressure sink. If a series connection with several sampling systems is possible, the error source due to the hydrogen origin for validation is eluded while ensuring a realistic refuelling according to the protocols (SAE J2601 etc.) except if one system can affect the other (in this risk is known in advance, the system in question shall be placed last).

Repeated sampling is recommended in order to evaluate the uncertainty contributions due to the sampling in particular random errors arising from the sampling. The calculation of the contribution of the sampling is however complex. The simplest method, called the duplicates method requires repeating the same nominal sampling protocol. Each duplicate is then analysed twice.

Finally, the quantity of hydrogen collected by any sampling system should be sufficient to be representative of the hydrogen dispensed. As described in the Deliverable D5 of MetHyTrucks, the minimum sample intake for HD FCEV sampling can be estimated at about 35 grams and shall be enough to allow all analyses needed.

Sample volumes vary widely by method (from 1 mL to 30 L). The chosen minimum sample intake reflects a balance between obtaining a representative sample and maintaining a practical size, while also considering material availability and transport regulations for flammable gas containers.

Results from an equivalence assessment campaign can be found in the deliverable 4 of MetHyTrucks [10]. This study provided the first comprehensive field-based validation of hydrogen sampling systems for HD refuelling as testing multiple systems under representative conditions offered valuable insight into sampling performance at hydrogen refuelling stations.

Results showed that three tested systems demonstrated equivalence for most regulated gaseous contaminants, supporting their suitability for hydrogen quality assessment when used within comparative frameworks. However, discrepancies for certain contaminants—particularly water and sulfur compounds—highlighted limits of equivalence testing (these species are sensitive to surface effects and pressure–temperature variations, which can differ across sampling systems).

6 Parameters at the HRS for different validation exercises

Table 3 gives an indication on how the parameters at the HRS station can be set so the conditions applied to systems to be compared are as similar as possible. This table has been written based on previous experiments and knowledge (for example tests done during MetroHyVe 2 and MetHyTrucks).

Table 3 – Overview of the parameters to be used during the different validation exercises

	Validation by comparison			
	Only parallel sampling systems (all HD or all LD)	Only direct sampling systems (all HD or all LD)	Parallel and direct sampling systems (all HD or all LD) (MHV2)	LD and HD sampling systems
Mode	Using refuelling protocol	Manual	Combination manual and refuelling protocol	Manual or using refuelling protocol
Refuelling protocol	SAE J2601-5 Wenger protocol (MCF-HF-G) Document the fuelling protocol applied, confirm refuelling proceeded under normal conditions	None / manual mode, set pressure	SAE J2601-5 [11] None for direct	
Nozzle	WEH TK16 HF & WEH TK17	use universal receptacle (e.g., WEH TK17-H2-35MPa-ENR)	use universal receptacle (e.g., WEH TK17-H2-35MPa-ENR)	HRS with receptacle compatible with HD and LD or use universal receptacle (e.g.,

				WEH TK17-H2-35MPa-ENR)
Flow	defined by the protocol	Regulated by the hardware and the cylinder but interesting to measure what flow was realized	Defined by protocol regulated by hardware	Max 60 g/s
Starting temperature	To be set (for example at -20 °C)	Matching delivery temperature	Set temperature for manual mode	To be set (for example at -20 °C)
Pressure	To be set (35 MPa better option than 70 MPa)	To be set at nominal pressure (35 MPa better option than 70 MPa)	35 MPa (HD) 70 MPa (LD)	35 MPa
Storage bank	Ensure homogeneity of the storage banks with station operator. Record which storage banks is used if possible	To be set so all systems tested receive the same gas (check that there is enough gas) or ensure homogeneity of storage bank	Define a storage bank for the two realisations	Defined storage bank to ensure LD and HD sample a similar % of the storage bank (if more than 1)
Installation	Sampling systems connected in series	Back-to-back to minimize risks for changes but manage risks that one sampler does affect the other	Back-to-back refuelling to minimize risks for changes but manage risks that one sampler affects the other	Back-to-back refuelling to minimize risks for changes but manage risks that one sampler affects the other

7 Operation of the sampling systems

It is important that the sample for gas and particulates is collected safely and representatively from the nozzle. Every system should have a tested operating protocol that has been verified. Another important aspect of the sampling is the safe venting of the skid or the sample at the end of the analysis.

Beforehand, attention should be paid to but not limited to the following technical aspects to collect a sufficiently representative sample [5].

- Adsorption, reaction and permeation of the sampling system
- Leaks and atmospheric diffusion in the sampling system
- Purging of the sampling system

All sampling systems should have a cleaning procedure for the cylinders and a sampling procedure involving purging to avoid false positive contamination which effectiveness has been demonstrated. Each of these procedures is different: different number of purges, different methods (the sampling cylinder arrives onsite pressurized, empty or under vacuum) and requires a different amount of time. This should be taken into consideration when planning the tests. The sampling strategy can be tested using a laboratory-based method as the one developed by NPL using certified reference materials (see Deliverable 5). Such validation is essential to ensure that samples collected from hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) are as representative as possible of the source hydrogen and free from artefacts introduced during sampling.

Selection of the sampling cylinder: Typically, samples of hydrogen containing inert gases and other non-

reactive components (e.g., carbon monoxide) at the levels specified in ISO 14687 are expected to remain stable in cylinders or other vessel types for periods of at least several months. Samples that contain impurities classified as reactive are expected to be unstable in time. Suitability of the cylinder's treatment must be established for compounds present individually in the gas: recent studies [9] have shown that DB Gold and Sulfinert stainless steel were the most suitable cylinders but even these are not suitable for all gaseous components to analyse for hydrogen purity. See compatibility table from MetroHyVe 2 in Annex 1. Further, in particular for low sulphur compounds, more data are needed for the suitability of cylinder treatments at trace levels and on the short-term the stability of sulphur compounds in these cylinders (see Deliverable D1 of the MetHyTrucks project). A recent study observed losses of mercaptans (15 %) and increase of H₂S (25 %) in DB Gold cylinders, which the authors indicated was most likely caused by catalytical effects. [12]

Filling pressure: Besides the material compatibility of the impurity in contact with the vessel, there are other factors that influence the stability of the analytes and their analysed amount fraction in the H₂ samples. Among them, the sample pressure. For components which adsorb on the cylinder wall, a pressure dependence is expected. Tests from the MetHyTrucks project provided useful insights (see report A1.6.4). For nitrogen, pressure effects are minimal (<1%), well within the 10% uncertainty limit of ISO 21087:2019.

Water shows greater variation, partly due to CRDS analyzer oscillations. At 40 MPa, lower results likely reflect adsorption losses on cylinder walls, which are more pronounced at low pressure. This may affect lower-pressure systems (e.g., 68 MPa), while higher-pressure systems are unlikely to show such effects.

8 Analysis of samples

In all steps, all samples need to be analysed in repeatable conditions within the shortest period of time (specified by the sampling system owner).

Utilisation of reference materials with low uncertainties (during analysis) and validated analytical methods with low measurement uncertainties are strongly recommended. Several reference materials were successfully produced and validated during MetroHyVe 2. For some impurities, reference materials are provided by the specialty gas industry of NMIs [12]. In most cases, only reference gas standards at higher amount fractions are available and these need to be dynamically diluted using a validated dilution system (e.g., based on mass flow controllers).

Good knowledge of the typical variation between sample containers is a prerequisite. It is also critical to use robust analytical methods to facilitate the evaluation of the results (inclusive to ensure that variations (if any) between the samples cannot be attributed to the analytical methods).

9 Validation with known amount of impurities

Understanding the behaviour of 14 contaminants in sampling conditions is complicated experimentally as it requires testing for their absence (avoid air leak) and for their presence (yield of recovery). Validating the absence of a contaminant is often feasible as most HRS have high purity hydrogen. The realization of sampling comparison will provide a higher degree of confidence if the amount fraction is slightly above the limit of detection (complete absence). The real challenge is the validation of presence and yield of recovery (i.e., 100% of H₂S from known sources). It would require finding a suitable contaminated HRS or an experimental site capable of achieving accurate contamination. Such a test facility is unlikely to be easily available as of today. Furthermore, it would require a high level of control of all contaminants and protocol to contaminate and decontaminate the HRS facility. It is a complex research project requiring a significant investment.

Another challenge is present for parallel sampling as it requires the gas to flow into a FCEV or a mock-up tank to allow some gas into the bleed line. This would require the system to accommodate a small mock-up tank (i.e., small type IV tank). The challenge will be in achieving the temperature and flow rate achieved at the HRS

required to have a large sample; however, such a small-scale experiment can provide a first understanding of the sampling system behaviour.

NPL has developed a prototype laboratory-based system that was tested for direct sampling and for parallel sampling. The lesson-learned from this first realization highlighted the importance of validating sampling systems and their associated purging procedures using gases with known contaminant amount fractions, as it leads to proposed improvements for the systems. Based on the tests performed, one system appears to benefit from a refined purging strategy, while the other may require improved surface passivation.

Another possibility will be to validate the sampling methodologies in a controlled environment where hydrogen is contaminated with known amounts of one or more relevant impurities. This approach will enable the accurate assessment of the recovery yield for these impurities. The MetHyTrucks project proposed a design of a living-HRS Platform (A3.3.5 [13]); a real-world validation environment featuring an integrated contamination system. This allows for the precise introduction of impurities to test the device's ability to detect them under actual refuelling conditions and wrote recommendations for the validation of hydrogen sampling devices, specifically targeting the unique requirements of HD-HRS.

10 Conclusions

Full validation of hydrogen sampling systems remains challenging due to the complexity of replicating real refuelling conditions and the difficulty of assessing trace contaminants with high confidence. A combined strategy—integrating field validation, laboratory testing, and equivalence assessment—therefore represents the most robust and pragmatic approach.

Field validation can more accurately capture actual operating conditions, while laboratory testing allows controlled evaluation using known contaminant concentrations. Equivalence assessment further complements these approaches by enabling comparison between systems under as similar conditions as possible, offering practical insight even when absolute reference values are not available.

Together, these methods provide a comprehensive framework for assessing performance, while acknowledging the inherent limitations and uncertainties associated with each approach.

However, further studies are needed to strengthen confidence in validation methodologies. In particular, additional work is required to improve the understanding of reactive species behaviour (e.g., water and sulfur compounds) and to carry out more in-depth validation of the recommendations outlined in the good-practice guide.

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12 Annex 1

Table 8 from deliverable 6 of MetroHyVe2 project

Table 8. Summary of results from the MetroHyVe 2 WP2 and WP3 results for contaminants at amount fractions close to or at the ISO 14687 threshold values. The table was based and updated from Arrhenius et al. [3]. The colour coding means green: suitable; yellow: suitable under limited conditions; red: unsuitable. Total sulphur has been assessed by taking the conservative approach. If one of the two sulphur compounds tested showed unsuitability, therefore the overall cylinder was considered unsuitable.

Component	Steel				Aluminium								
	Stainless steel Sulfinert®	Manganese steel	ALD-Coated steel	Untreated stainless steel	SPECTRA-SEAL	Untreated SGS	H2 Mobility	Aculife VIII	Aculife III	White top	AlphaTech	Performax	DB Gold
He	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
N ₂	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	Suit
Ar	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
CO ₂	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
CO	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
Tot S	Uns ₁ stab**	Uns ₁ stab*	Uns ₁ il	i.d.	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ stab**	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ stab**	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Uns ₁ stab†
H ₂ S	Uns ₁ stab**	Uns ₁ stab*	Uns ₁ il	i.d.	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ stab**	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ stab**	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Suit†
OCS	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Uns ₁ stab
HCl	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Suit	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ il	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Suit
CCl ₂ H ₂	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
CH ₂ O	Suit	Uns ₁ stab*	Uns ₁ stab**	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	Suit
CH ₂ OH	Suit	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ il	i.d.	Suit	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Uns ₁ il	Uns ₁ il	Uns ₁ il	i.d.	Suit
NH ₃	Suit	Uns ₁ il-stab	Uns ₁ stab	i.d.	Uns ₁ il	Uns ₁ il	Suit	i.d.	Suit	Uns ₁ il	Uns ₁ il-stab	i.d.	Suit
O ₂	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
H ₂ O	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
C ₃ H ₈	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit	i.d.	i.d.	Suit
CH ₄	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	i.d.	X	Suit	X	X	Suit
C ₂ H ₆	Suit	X	X	X	Suit	Suit	Suit	X	X	Suit	X	X	Suit

X should be suitable (no published data available)
i.d. insufficient data
+ Additional sulphur containing components were present in the gas cylinder
Suit Stable to gravimetric amount fraction within 95% confidence level for duration of the study (4 months)
Uns Unsuitable for sampling this compound at EN 17124 amount fraction
il Unsuitability due to an initial loss of the compound compared to gravimetric value
Stab Unsuitability due to compound instability in the cylinder for the duration of the study
+ Unstable but suitable for very short time (1-2 week), stability uncertainty including decay is similar to stable cylinders for this period. The stability period is provided in brackets, only useful for very short transport
** Unstable but suitable for short time (1-2 month), stability uncertainty including decay is similar to stable cylinders for this period. The stability period is provided in brackets, only useful for short transport